

A CLUSTER APPROACH TO THE ORGANIZATION OF MODERN FRUIT AND VEGETABLE AGRO-INDUSTRY

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Abstract: The cluster approach is effectively used to provide the population with quality agricultural products due to the formation of efficient high-tech and competitive agro-industrial production based on innovative development. Currently, the processes of integration based on the clustering of agriculture and processing industry are coming to the fore in the development of the agro-industrial complex. The article describes the need to organize agroclusters, its goals and tasks. Opinions were also given about the agrocluster, which operates in the cultivation, processing and sale of fruits and vegetables in Namangan region. Recommendations are given for the development of agroclusters in the regions.

Key words: food safety, effective mechanism, technical modernization, domestic and foreign markets, fruits and vegetables, cash crops, suppliers, manufacturers, cost-effective and transparent communication, increasing competitiveness of products, increasing scientific and technical potential, cooperation further development, development of investment projects.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture of any country is one of the main components of the economy that ensures food security. Providing the population with essential food products is the most important task. Its implementation depends on the development of agriculture, enterprises engaged in product processing, as well as service and social spheres.

In order to create an effective mechanism for carrying out economic reforms in agriculture, it is necessary to introduce technical modernization, scientific-practical, financial, material-technical and other resources, as well as the development of economic relations.

Unlike developed agricultural countries, the agricultural producers of our country do not fully apply the breeding, technical, technological, organizational and other achievements of science, which makes local products uncompetitive. In this regard, the problem of managing development processes and mechanisms for agriculture based on the formation of an agricultural cluster remains relevant.

The main part

The increasing strategic importance of the development of agriculture in the context of the aggravation of food problems in the world requires its development using the latest scientific and technical progress achieved in the world economy.

Based on the fact that the domestic and foreign markets have great opportunities to supply high-quality and affordable agricultural products - fruits and vegetables, pulse crops, a number of measures aimed at providing the population with locally processed agricultural products have been implemented. events and government decisions were taken. It is for this reason that consistent work is being carried out in our republic to improve the varieties of these products, expand the acreage and volume of raw materials, establish new enterprises for processing, modernize the existing ones, and technical and technological re-equipment.

At the moment, despite the comprehensive measures implemented, the production, harvesting, transportation, storage, processing, packaging and domestic and foreign markets of agricultural food products in order to supply the population with the required quantity and quality a number of shortcomings, problems and imbalances related to sales remain [5]. Among them - the lack of the necessary amount of raw materials for processing and the lack of timely supply; as a result of the purchase of agricultural products by processing enterprises at low prices, their material interest is low; due to the lack of special equipment in the transportation of products, quality deterioration and wastage; lack of special warehouse buildings and freezers for storing agricultural products; lack of qualified specialists in the management and use of technologies of processing enterprises; We can list the lack of widespread production of glass containers of various sizes and designs for packaging recycled products and their shortage.

In such conditions, the main factor of sustainable development of agriculture is the establishment of agroclusters. The main goal of creating an agricultural cluster is to increase production efficiency by obtaining maximum economic, social and environmental benefits. In order to implement the cluster model of the development of the agro-industrial complex, it is necessary to ensure the fulfillment of certain conditions [3]:

- balance of economic, financial and legal interests of cluster participants;
- development of a unified information environment in the digital economy;
- a systematic approach to management of investment and innovation processes and establishment of consulting activities in the agricultural cluster;
- development of intra-network integration in the cluster.

The main tasks of agro-industry clusters are as follows:

- wide introduction of modern methods of growing fruits and vegetables and other agricultural crops, scientific achievements and advanced innovation and water-saving irrigation technologies;
- use of effective methods and technologies of deep processing of fruit and vegetable products, attracting direct foreign investments;
- creation of a modern "in-vitro" laboratory and nurseries for growing disease-free fruit tree seedlings;
- increasing export volumes by producing value-added and competitive products;
- the increase of soil fertility and agricultural crop yield, rational and efficient use of land and implementation of measures for their protection.

Today, more than 20 fruit and vegetable clusters are operating in Namangan region. It is planned to allocate 50 % of the total land specialized in fruit and vegetable growing in the province. There are 50,000 hectares of fruit and vegetable growing land in the region. In the first stage, 38,500 hectares are being specialized [6].

For example, a total of 3171 hectares of land in Iskavot region of Yangi-Kurgan district are growing several products. Within 2 years, we are specializing these 3171 hectares in garden, vegetables and potatoes. Of course, climatic and natural conditions are taken into account in the specialization of the area for a certain crop

In accordance with the President's decision No. PQ-4941 dated January 11, 2021 on measures to develop fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture in Kosonsoy, Chortoq and Yangikurgan districts of Namangan region, increasing the volume of production, processing and sale of fruit and vegetable products A number of works are being carried out in order to introduce modern methods, attract direct investments to the industry, and create new jobs.

On November 17, 2021, an agreement on the implementation of an investment project on the establishment of a fruit and vegetable cluster specializing in the cultivation of fruit and vegetable products in Namangan region was signed between the administration of Namangan region and the company "Sibirskoe zdorove" of the Russian Federation. In order to attract foreign direct investments in the amount of 20.9 million US dollars for the purpose of establishing production and processing capacities of fruit and vegetable products by the foreign enterprise "Siberian Wellness-Namangan" LLC; Formation of the initial authorized fund (capital) of the enterprise by the company "Sibirskoe zdorove", which is the founder of the foreign enterprise "Siberian Wellness-Namangan" LLC; The joint venture "Namangan

sharbati” LLC plans to attract investment funds in the amount of 10 million US dollars for the purpose of establishing new intensive gardens [1].

Table 1

Investment projects implemented by the joint venture “Namangan sharbati” LLC in 2022-2025 forecast parameters

No	Name of the investment project	Estimated cost of the project (million USD)	Including: own funds of the project initiator (million USD)	Implementation period
1.	Implementation of agrotechnical measures to prepare land for planting	0.05	0.05	2022-2023 years
2.	Purchase of intensive fruit tree seedlings	3.14	3.14	2022-2023 years
3.	Digging wells and building a pumping station for water extraction	0.11	0.11	2022-2023 years
4.	Introduction of drip irrigation system	0.80	0.80	2022-2023 years
5.	Organization of nursery laboratory	0.02	0.02	2022-2024 years
6.	Construction of a fruit processing plant	5.77	5.77	2022-2025 years
7.	Purchase of agricultural machinery and aggregates	0.09	0.09	2022-2025 years
8.	Other expenses	0.03	0.03	2022-2023 years
	Total:	10.0	10.0	

It is planned to attract investment funds in the amount of 10 million US dollars for the purpose of establishing new intensive gardens by the joint venture “Namangan sharbati” LLC.

The advantages for enterprises when entering a cluster are: the availability of a raw material base, sales markets, free exchange of information and knowledge, modernization of infrastructure facilities, the possibility of diversification of activities. At the same time, there is a decrease in the risk associated with external and internal conditions (seasonality, natural-climatic conditions, etc.). These advantages increase production volume and reduce production costs [4]. The entry of an agro-industrial enterprise into the cluster will improve its provision of raw materials, materials, equipment and labor[7;8].

If we compare the interests of the parties in the formation of agricultural clusters, first of all, we should highlight regional and local authorities. In this way, jobs are created, taxes go to the local budget, the region is provided with socially important food products and services [2].

In the second place, personal assistant estates and individual entrepreneurs in rural areas are interested. It is important for them to participate in the processes of selling surplus products (milk, meat, poultry, eggs, wool, leather and by-products) and obtaining a permanent source of income. Also, their interests - in modern technologies and agricultural techniques in the production process, in replacing manual labor with more modern mechanized and automated techniques and technologies, in the use of information related to the field in private farms, in bringing modern varieties of plants and productive breeds of animals can be seen on arrival.

One of the important aspects of the organization of an agrocluster is the high level of trust of its participants in each other through the implementation of collaborative projects that include the production, processing, sale, and scientific research processes of agricultural products.

Conclusion

The agro-industry cluster allows the enterprise to establish cost-effective and transparent relations between suppliers and producers. The advantages of creating a cluster for local authorities will be to increase the number of taxpayers and the taxable base, and to simplify the procedure for monitoring the activities of enterprises included in the cluster. The success of the implementation of the cluster strategy in the region depends on the efficiency of the system of innovative processes. Improving the investment environment in agricultural sectors and increasing their competitiveness leads to an increase in the economic efficiency of the regional agro-industrial complex.

We recommend the following for the development of agroclusters in the regions: increase the competitiveness of the products of local agricultural enterprises; increase

the scientific and technical potential of the agro-industrial complex and its effective use; integration; further development of cooperation and internationalization; establishment of joint ventures, introduction of new techniques; activation of development and implementation of investment projects; formation of a more capacious progressive market and strengthening of wholesale trade, etc.

The establishment of an agro-industrial cluster with developed production, sales, information and other services in the region will have a positive effect on increasing the investment attractiveness of the region, increasing employment and the well-being of rural residents, developing other sectors of the region's economy, and accelerating the processes of import substitution.

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